

Electrometric Study on Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) Complexes of Isopropylmercaptan and Determination of their Solubility Products

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The complexation of copper (Cu^{+2}), mercury (Hg^{+2}) and silver (Ag^+) ion with isopropylmercaptan has been studied in 25% (V/V) ethanolic media employing potentiometric, conductometric and amperometric titration techniques. Copper and mercury ions form 1:2 complex while silver ion shows the formation of 1:1 complex. Equilibrium constants and solubility products of these complexes have been evaluated by Ringbom's method at 10°, 20° and 30°. The overall changes in thermodynamic functions ΔG , ΔH and ΔS accompanying complexation have also been determined at 20° with the help of an isobar and Gibb's Helmholtz equation.

THIOLS containing -SH group, have a tendency to form complexes with metals. Several metal complexes of thiols have already been studied by Saxena and co-workers¹⁻³, which have important applications in various disciplines like pharmaceutical, tanning and resin industries. The present communication reports the composition of sparingly soluble complexes of Cu(II), Hg(II), Ag(I) ions with isopropylmercaptan by amperometric, conductometric, potentiometric methods and determination of their equilibrium constants and solubility products at different temperatures.

Experimental

Isopropylmercaptan $[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH.SH}]$, referred herein as ISH] and other chemicals used were of AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade. Freshly prepared solutions were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air-oxidation.

Potentiometric and conductometric titrations, both direct and reverse, were performed in an inert atmosphere of Nitrogen using a Cambridge bench pH-meter and an electronic eye type conductometer. In both the direct titrations, title metal ions had the concentration $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ and were titrated against 0.1M ISH while in the reverse titrations $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH and $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH titrated against $5 \times 10^{-2} M$ title metal ions in the potentiometric and conductometric titrations, respectively. 25 ml of the titre solution in 25% (V/V) ethanol was used in each case and the end-points corresponding to the complex formation were obtained from the breaks in the titration curves.

Amperometric titrations were performed in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen using a manual polarograph with a scalamp galvanometer as current

recorder and S.C.E. as reference electrode. The capillary used had the following characteristics in 25% (V/V) ethanol, 0.2M NaClO_4 and 0.002% Triton-X-100 at -0.7V vs S.C.E. with h_{off} value being 38.1 cm., $m = 1.390 \text{ mg/sec.}$, $t = 4.3 \text{ sec./drop.}$ 25 ml solution of the titre in 25% ethanol contained $3 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal ion, 0.2M NaClO_4 and 0.002% Triton-X-100 and the concentration of the titrant used was $5 \times 10^{-2} M$ ISH in ethanol.

Results and Discussion

As reported earlier⁴, isopropylmercaptan produces a diffusion controlled anodic wave associated with a pre-wave at d.m.e. It is observed that at -0.7V vs S.C.E., the metals under investigation are reducible but ISH shows inert behaviour. Hence amperometric titrations at -0.7V were carried out in 25% ethanol, 0.2M NaClO_4 and 0.002% Triton-X-100 for determining the composition, equilibrium constants and solubility products of the complexes at different temperatures.

Stoichiometry :

For establishing the stoichiometry of the complex species formed during the interaction of metal ion and ISH, a series of conductometric, potentiometric and amperometric titrations were carried out using different concentration of reactants both by direct and reverse methods (Fig. 1). The equivalence points in the titrations curves corresponded to the formation of 1:2 complex for Cu(II), Hg(II) and 1:1 for Ag(I) in accordance with the following equations.

For 1:2 complex :

(where M^{+2} stands for Cu^{+2} , Hg^{+2}) ... (1)

For 1 : 1 complex :

Fig. 1(a) Curves 1, 2, 3—conductometric titrations of 25 ml solutions containing $4 \times 10^{-2} M$ ISH against (M/20) Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Ag^+ (metal nitrates) respectively.
 Fig. 1(b) Curves 4, 5, 6—conductometric titrations of 25 ml. solution containing $4 \times 10^{-2} M$, Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Ag^+ respectively against 0.1M ISH.

Equilibrium constants and solubility products : The values of equilibrium constants for the complexation reactions between metal ion and the ligand have been determined by Ringbom's method⁵. The following equation⁶ has been used for evaluating K_t , the conditional or formal equilibrium constant.

$$\frac{(i - i_r)(1 + rf)}{(i_0 - i_r)} = \frac{(1 - f) + [(1 - f)^2 + 4(1 + rf)^2 / K_t (C_M^0)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2} \quad \dots (3)$$

where r is the dilution parameter ($r = C_M^0 / C_x$) and f is the titration parameter defined by the equation

$$f = Z \frac{V_x C_x}{V_0 C_M^0} \quad \dots (4)$$

Z being the number of moles of the titre which react with each mole of the titrant ; in the present case $Z = 0.5$ for $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ and 1 for $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$. C_M^0 and i_0 are the initial concentration and limiting current of the metal ion respectively ; i_r and i are respectively the residual current and the current at any titration point. The titration parameter f becomes equal to unity at the equivalence point.

When a reducible ion is titrated with an inert one to give a precipitate, equation(3) at the equivalence point can be written as

$$K_t = \left(\frac{1}{C_M^0} \times \frac{i_0 - i_r}{i - i_r} \right)^2 \quad \dots (5)$$

from which the value of K_t under the experimental conditions of the titration can be obtained. The value of the $\frac{i_0 - i_r}{i - i_r}$ at the equivalence point was obtained from the plot of $\frac{i - i_r}{i_0 - i_r} \times \frac{V_0 + v}{V_0}$ vs f (Fig. 2). $\frac{V_0 + v}{V_0}$ is the volume correction factor at any titration point.

Fig. 2 Curves 1, 2, 3—plot for $\frac{i - i_r}{i_0 - i_r} \times \frac{V_0 + v}{V_0}$ vs f for Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} respectively at 10° .

TABLE 1—VALUES OF K_t AND K_s FOR $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ AND $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ COMPLEXES OF ISOPROPYLMERCAPTAN AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Complex	Equilibrium constant (K_t)			Solubility product (K_s)		
	10°	20°	30°	10°	20°	30°
$\text{Cu}(\text{II})$	12.35×10^7	3.67×10^7	1.98×10^7	8.18×10^{-9}	27.23×10^{-9}	50.63×10^{-9}
$\text{Hg}(\text{II})$	27.44×10^7	6.95×10^7	4.45×10^7	3.60×10^{-9}	14.40×10^{-9}	22.49×10^{-9}
$\text{Ag}(\text{I})$	15.37×10^6	11.11×10^6	7.11×10^6	6.51×10^{-9}	9.01×10^{-9}	14.06×10^{-9}

In the absence of any side reaction that could consume either ion, K_t for the precipitation titration is the reciprocal of the solubility product. Thus solubility products, K_s for Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) complexes may also be evaluated and values of K_t and K_s for different complexes of ISH at three different temperatures are given in Table 1.

Thermodynamic functions: The values of changes in the free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS), accompanying the complexation reactions have been determined at 20° with the help of standard equations⁷. The value of ΔG is obtained from the expression $\Delta G = -RT \ln K_t$, where K_t is the equilibrium constant. ΔH is determined with the help of an isobar $\frac{d \ln K_t}{dt} = \frac{\Delta H}{RT^2}$ which may be written as $\frac{d \log K_t}{d(1/T)} = -\frac{\Delta H}{4.57}$. The values of $\log K_t$ obtained at different temperatures are plotted as a function of $1/T$. The gradient of the tangent drawn at the point corresponding to 20° is determined and equated to $-\frac{\Delta H}{4.57}$. ΔS is then evaluated from the relation $\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE—2 THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS FOR CU(II), HG(II) AND AG(I) COMPLEXES OF ISOPROPYLMERCAPTAN AT 20°

Metal Complex	ΔG (K cal/mole)	ΔH (K cal/mole)	ΔS (cal/deg/mole)
Cu(II)	-10.14	-13.71	-12.18
Hg(II)	-10.52	-13.41	-9.83
Ag(I)	-9.45	-6.74	+9.25

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